

1ST HANRAHAN LECTURE

GEOTECHNICAL PROPERTIES OF IRISH GLACIAL AND INTERGLACIAL SOILS

ERIC R FARRELL, AGL Consulting.

Paper presented to the Institution of Engineers of Ireland, 19th April 2016

Deep cutting in unsorted till on M7 near Mayfield, Co. Kildare

SYNOPSIS

This paper reviews the current state-of-the-art in relation to geotechnical design in unsorted till deposits, commonly called boulder clays by engineers or diamictons by geologists, generally taking the topics discussed by Prof. Eamon Hanrahan in his seminal work on Irish tills of 1977. These topics include the permeability, stiffness, and consolidation characteristics of these deposits, together with their undrained and drained behaviour. The geological background to the deposition of these tills is discussed and the available information on the presence of interglacial soils around the country is presented. Where possible, the practical experience from working with these deposits is compared with predictions made from field or laboratory test results, for example, in settlement assessment of foundations, slope stability and in earthworks.

Whilst most of Ireland is covered with stony boulder clays, which is the main topic of the paper, the geotechnical parameters of a fine grained till encountered on the east coast, known as Irish Sea till or colloquially as Macamore Clay, are discussed and the implications of this on slope stability is investigated.

INTRODUCTION

The Pleistocene Epoch (Ice Age) had a devastating effect on the Irish landscape in that it gave rise to the erosion of most of the earlier soils and weak rocks and deposited a complex mixture of soils and soil types, within or on which much of our structures and infrastructures are constructed. Hanrahan (1977) described the processes of the formation and some of the geotechnical properties of these legacy soils, however the experience gained from research and construction/design since that time has given additional information which this paper presents and reviews.

The Pleistocene Epoch was not a constant cold low temperature period but included warm periods in which Ireland experienced climates similar to today. This paper includes an overview of the Pleistocene Epoch and discusses the relic soils evident today from the warm periods. The main focus of the paper is on the geotechnical properties of those soils which are 'unsorted' and which therefore comprise a mixture of particle sizes. Commonly called boulder clays, these soils comprise the very stiff lodgement tills as well as those unsorted meltwater tills but which in geological terminology would be called 'diamictons'. These soils are well graded up to gravels size particles which generally make it difficult to determine the relevant geotechnical parameters from undisturbed samples and field tests, consequently much of design practice is related to simple tests together with general experience for all but for major projects. This paper looks at the general experience of engineering in these soils over the last 40 years.

The Irish Sea till, which is found along the east and some of the southern coast of Ireland, is attributed to a major ice flow down the Irish Sea during the Pleistocene Epoch. The geotechnical properties of this till, which is also colloquially called Macamore Clay, differ from much of the till found elsewhere in Ireland and are also discussed in this paper.

GEOLOGICAL BACKGROUND

The Quaternary Period (2.3Ma to present) followed the warm-temperature or sub-tropical conditions of the Tertiary Period (65 to 2.3 Ma) during which the landscape experienced erosion, limestone solution and deep weathering bedrock (Mitchell, 1980, 1985), with karstification of the limestone. The glaciation of the country during the Pleistocene Epoch (2.3Ma to 10ka) removed most of the Tertiary deposits and there are only few remnants remaining. Such deposits that do exist are to be found in the interbasaltic beds of the basalt plateau in the north-east and as in-fills and weathered residues within karstic depressions within Carboniferous limestone (Coxon, 2001).

The source, age, method of deposition and weathering conditions of the various soils and rocks formed during the Pleistocene period are of relevance when interpreting geotechnical parameters. The temperature changes during the Pleistocene, which were mainly controlled by orbital relationships until recent anthropological interference (Hays et al., 1976), have been well researched. Records from deep marine and lacustrine deposits show that the temperature declined during the latter period of the Tertiary and ended with numerous step-like changes over the last 2.3 Ma (Coxon, 2001). Early temperature cycles indicate a

predominantly 41ka period while the latter stages to present (0.9 Ma to present) suggest that the cold stages occur over 100 ka intervals (Shackleton and Opdyke, 1976). The climate signals are preserved in oxygen isotope records from deep sea marine sediments and ice core (Shackleton et al, 1991;Funnel 1995). High values of the oxygen isotope ^{18}O in relation to the more numerous ^{16}O would be expected to represent a cold period and low values would represent warmer spells. The data has been used to assign marine isotope stages (MIS) to represent warm and cold spells, starting with the present as MIS1, with the even numbers representing high values of O^{18} and represent cold spells and the odd numbers are troughs representing warm interglacial intervals, and extends up to MIS104 2.6 million years ago. The cyclical nature of the cold periods is clearly evident in these temperature records as can be seen from Figure 1. The Russian station at Vostok on the Antarctica is the source of the estimated temperature changes shown in Figure 2, but records are also available from the Concordia and Kohnen stations, the latter as part of the European Project for Ice Coring in the Antarctica (EPICA). Four glacial periods, to about 420ka, can be interpreted from the Vostok ice core whilst the EPICA data extends to about 800ka.

Figure 1 Temperature changes over the last 5 million years (by R Rohde based on Lisiecke & Raymo,2005).

Figure 2 Temperature anomalies from Vostok ice core (Jouzel et al. 1987; Jouzel et al. 1993; Jouzel et al. 1996; Jouzel et al. 1996; Petit et al. 1999)

The last glacial maximum (LGM) was about 20 to 24 ka before present (BP) and deglaciation in the Northern Hemisphere began about 19ka and in the Antarctic about 14.5ka years BP. The data show that the last glaciation (Midlandian) began at the end of the Eemian interglacial period (also called the Ipswichian, MIS5e) about 120ka ago, which lasted in excess of 20ka, and was preceded by the Munsterian glaciation (MIS 6). Ireland experienced periods of relatively warmer weather (interstadials) and colder weather (stadials) even within the Midlandian, as can be seen from the temperature variations on Figure 2. The general sea level at the end of the last glaciation was about 125m below its present level and it rose rapidly during the deglaciation of the Antarctic.

Despite the relatively numerous warm periods within the Pleistocene during which erosion and deposition would be expected to occur, the glacial topography of today is almost totally the product of the last glaciation (Midlandian). Until recently it was considered that the two major moraine belts, the South Ireland End Moraine (SIEM) and the Killumney End Moraine (KM) which are shown on Figure 3, represented the limits of the last glaciation (Midlandian) and that the glacial soils between these moraines were from the earlier Munsterian glaciation. This division was largely based on morpho-stratigraphic grounds as the area between these moraines is characterised by *'subdued morphologies, a distinct lack of 'fresh' glacial bedforms, deep-weathering profiles and abundant periglacial features, contrasting with the absence of such characteristics in the area of Younger Drift glaciated by the Midlandian'* (O'Cofaigh & Evans, 2015). Fossil pingos found between the moraines (Mitchell 1973) are interesting legacy examples of such periglacial features. Advances in the methods of dating deposits led to O'Cofaigh & Evans (2007) and O'Cofaigh et al (2012), to conclude that the Irish Sea Till along the south coast was formed during an ice advance after about 24 ka BP. This indicated that most of southern Ireland must have been glaciated during the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM). The current view is that there was a brief and rapid advance of the Irish Sea ice sheet to its maximum limit far south in the Celtic Sea during the LGM followed by a relatively rapid deglaciation and ice retreat before stabilising at the end locations of the SIEM and KM end moraines (Scourse et al. 1990, Praeg et al. 2015). The drift deposits between these end moraines may be the product of paraglacial sedimentation and suggests that the front of the ice-sheet may have stabilised at these locations for some time. Coxon (2001) considers that the surviving soil from the last interglacial is limited to a reworked ball of organic sediment found in Knocknacran, Co. Monaghan, however there are about thirteen sites where soil strata have been attributed to an earlier glaciation (Gortian, not definitively dated, 198ka to 252ka or 302ka to 338ka). Examples of pre-Gortian deposits are limited to infilling of solution features in limestone.

Figure 3 South Ireland End Moraine and Killumney Moraine (from O'Cofaigh et al. 2012).

The author encountered perhaps the most extensive example of an interglacial deposit when involved with the ground investigation for the Emmett Bridge (then called the Custom House South Bridge) in Cork with Soil Mechanics Ltd. in 1979. The deposit, which was 18.1m thick and underlay

about 18m of gravels, was called 'Pond Alluvium' at that time but subsequent research confirmed that it was an interglacial deposit of probably Gortian age (Source et al., 1992). Coxon and Dowling (2015) identified other sites – see Figure 4, and recovered samples from close to the Emmett Bridge, from Douglas where it was 10.4m thick and from Carricktwohill where it was 17.3m thick. It was encountered below 4 to 5m of alluvium (and some made ground) at the latter two sites. The sediment is stiff to very stiff, as is evident from the N_{SPT} values and index results against elevation on Figures 5 and 6. The measured undrained shear strength (c_u) in unconsolidated undrained triaxial test on U100 samples, were 90, 160 and 288kPa, however these results would have been affected by sample disturbance. The results of a standard oedometer test on samples from 21.5m (CS8-27) and 23.4m (CS8-30) depth given on Figure 7.

Figure 4 From: Geology of Ireland, Ed. C H Holland, 2001

Figure 5 N_{SPT} vs. elevation

Figure 6 Index tests of Gortian sediment

Figure 7 Oedometer results on sample of Gortian sediment.

The complex deposition conditions under which glacial soils have been formed and the variety of sediments that fall within the general title of glacial tills is well documented in Hanrahan (1977), Coxon (2001) and Boulton & Paul (1976). Although the glacial soils which currently dominate the Irish landscape were almost entirely the product of the last (Midlandian) glaciation, there was significant variation in the depositional environment and also in the direction of glacial ice flow. The Quaternary maps of the Geological Survey of Ireland are a useful source of information on the distribution of glacial deposits. These maps classify the till units mainly on the basis of lithology of the stones (between 5-10mm in size) within the till (Warren, 1991); however field observations regarding the texture are also recorded. The primary purpose of these maps is to show the origin of the till and the ice flow directions. The direction of flow within the Midlandian was not constant as is evident from the Courtmacsherry exposure mapped by O Cofaigh et al (2012) where a wave cut bedrock platform was overlaid by a bedded gravel layer (MIS 4-3 of the last cold stage about 45 ka to 65 ka, and therefore postdates the last interglacial), which is overlain by what is considered to be a periglacial slope deposit (head) which in turn is overlain by Irish Sea Till (shells dated <cal. 24 ka, glacitectonised and not a

glaciomarine deposit). These deposits are overlain by a layer of glaciolacustrine and glacio fluvial sediments and a subglacial till originating from inland, representing grounded ice movement from Cork/Kerry. The variations during the Midlandian are also evident from the work of McCabe and Hoare (1978) and others. The work of Skipper et al (2005) on the deep section of the Dublin boulder clay exposed in the cut and cover section of the Dublin Port Tunnel clearly showed four different formations within the overall deposit. The upper formation is the product of weathering and oxidation of the fine particles which has resulted in the Dublin brown boulder clay (Farrell et al.1995a). These studies illustrate the complexity of glacial deposits encountered in this country.

While much of the country is covered by stony glacial deposits, the Irish Sea till on the south east of the country are predominantly stiff fine grained soils and therefore have different characteristics. These tills are discussed in later sections of this paper.

LOW FINES DIAMICTONS

The use of the term 'boulder clay' is considered to be inappropriate for those low fines unsorted glacial deposits which do not have sufficient fines to maintain suction pressure for any significant period of time when excavated and therefore to not exhibit 'cohesion' in engineering terms, yet the term 'glacial till' is too broad a category as it could be considered to include water laid glacial material. These low fines unsorted deposits are called low fines diamictons in this paper to avoid any suggestion that their behaviour is representative of a fine grained soil. These low fines diamictons present particular geotechnical challenges in relation to sampling and in-situ testing and also in relation to their handling in earthworks. These would be unsorted glacial soils with fines contents (% of particles < 63µm) between about 15% to 30%, thus their engineering behaviour is marginal between that of a fine grained and coarse grained material in many design situations. Their grading would not conform strictly to the straight line grading of lodgement tills on particle size distribution (PSD) plots (Hanrahan, 1977) and examples of such tills from O'Donnell (2012) are shown on Figure 8. The difficulty of sampling these soils arises from the gravel content which restricts driving or pushing in samples and from the inability of the soil to hold suction pressure. These properties also affect the in-situ testing of these soils and, from the experience of the author, poor results have been obtained when using such methods as pressuremeter, CPT and Marchetti dilatometer testing. The SPT and dynamic probes do give some indication of the in-situ condition but these are very crude instruments and any empirical correlation between the blow counts for a specified penetration and geotechnical parameters must be treated with caution. Trial pit exposures do not necessarily indicate their undisturbed properties due to seepage pressures giving a visual impression of a 'soft' soil. Owing to the lack of good quality test data on such soils for most projects, many designs are necessarily based on 'engineering judgement and experience'.

The classification of these glacial soils, based on PSDs and index tests, is very important if engineering judgement is to be applied correctly. In that regard the classification system in BS5930:1999 & 2015 requires modification if the

important features of the behaviour are to be captured (Farrell, 2010). It is recommended that a glacial deposit should only be called a ‘Clay’ or ‘Silt’ if the fines content is equal to or greater than 35% in order to reflect a cohesive soil with a reasonable ‘stand-up time’ or ability to hold suctions, in say a 3m high vertical face, and that the unsorted tills with lesser fines be termed typically clayey or very clayey sandy Gravels, with the terms representative of their nature and proportion. In order to overcome the BS requirement that minor constituents be described as ‘slightly sandy/slightly gravelly’ if less than 35% by weight, it would be necessary to alter the classification system in the current BS5930:2015 to permit the use of the terms sandy and gravelly for ‘boulder clay type soils’ when both the sand and the gravel constituents exceed 20% and where the combined percentage of sand and gravel exceeds 50%.

Figure 8 Example of low fines diamictons (O’Donnell, 2012)

SETTLEMENT PARAMETERS

While very limited research has been carried out into the stiffness and consolidation characteristics of low fines diamictons, it is useful to consider the considerable knowledge that has been accumulated in recent years on the Dublin black boulder clay. This knowledge emanated from Dublin Port Tunnel and other deep excavations in that city which have combined, in many cases, sophisticated laboratory testing, finite element predictions of ground movement and actual measurement of ground movements during and after construction. The challenge is to extend the behavioural models developed for this deposit to the low fine diamictons which are more difficult to sample and to test.

The stiffness of the Dublin black boulder clay (DBC), in-line with other soils, is complex as it has a non-linear stress/strain relationship which also depends on the effective confining stress, on stress history and of course on whether it is loaded in an undrained or drained condition. Soil models have been developed which attempt to incorporate these factors, such as the hardening soil model used in the software program Plaxis (Schanz et al., 1999; Benz, 2006). This soil model has been used in research (Lawler et al., 2011) and on large projects. The very stiff DBC was also numerically modelled in Kovacevic et al. (2008) and Kovacevic et al. (2015) using the Imperial College finite element software. These are examples of sophisticated geotechnical analyses which can be carried out on projects with large budgets, however the more mundane approach

taken in routine design will be discussed in the following sections of this paper.

It is useful to consider the parameters typically used to define the non-linear behaviour of DBC, which are the small strain stiffness, namely E_0 and the secant modulus E_{50} , which are illustrated on Figure 9. The small strain stiffness of DBC can be determined from undisturbed (GeoBoreS) samples using local strain measurements and Bender elements and from in-situ testing using geophysics, typically MASW. The small strain shear modulus (G_0) values determined from MASW tests and from bender elements for a site in Dublin city central are shown on Figure 10. The small strain undrained modulus, E_0 , can be determined from G_0 using the relationship $2G=E/(1+\mu)$, with $\mu=\mu_u=0.5$. Similarly the small strain drained modulus, E_0' can be determined from the same equation with the appropriate μ' value, which is typically taken as 0.2. The effective stress secant moduli, E_{50}' , and its variation with confining stress (p_0'), as determined by Lawler et al. (2011), is shown on Figure 11. The small strain stiffness of the DBC is about 6 to 8 times stiffer than that measured in London Clay (Kovacevic et al., 2008) and this accounts for the relatively small movement reported around deep excavations in these deposits (Lawler et al. 2011; Long et al., 2012). The stress history of glacial deposits is also relevant when developing a soil model and, for example, the yield stress in 1-D compression determined by Lawler et al. (2011) on samples for undisturbed till in a very stiff oedometer test was about 1500kPa (see Figure 12), which compares favourably with a value of 1300±300kPa estimated by Lehane & Simpson (2000). The stiffness parameters determined by Lawler et al. (2011), when used in the hardening soil model (HSM), reasonably predict the measured deformations of the 1.5m square Tallaght pad footing given in Farrell et al (1987), as can be seen from Figure 13. For routine foundation design, which is generally carried out assuming a linear elastic E' soil, a value of 80 MPa is generally considered appropriate for the DBC for very high compressive stresses. However it is an approximation of the non-linear response, and from inspection of Figure 13, is conservative for more typical bearing stresses which would be of the order of 400kPa. The stiffness also depends on the loading situation and $E' \approx 150$ MPa more closely models the behaviour of a driven pile (Farrell et al. 1995b). Lawler et al. (2011) showed that a linear elastic Mohr-Coulomb soil model grossly overestimated the deformations around excavations.

Figure 9 Example of E_0 and E_{50} on triaxial test result

Figure 10 Variation in G_0 with p' (courtesy of AGL Consulting)

Figure 11 Variation in E_{50}' with p' (Lawlor et al., 2011)

Figure 12 Oedometer tests on DBC (Lawlor et al., 2011)

Figure 13 Tallaght Trial foundation test on DBC

The extensive laboratory and field research into the stiffness of DBC has not been matched on other tills in Ireland, consequently there is very limited data on the behaviour of low fines diamictons or other tills outside Dublin. In the absence of reliable laboratory or field test methods, recourse is usually made in routine design to empirical correlations with the crude standard penetration test values, usually the Stroud & Bulter (1975) empirical relationship between E_v'/N_{SPT} and I_p (where E_v' is the vertical drained secant modulus and I_p the Plasticity Index) for overconsolidated soils. Stroud & Butler (1975) also give a relationship for coefficient of volume compressibility (m_v) to $1/f_2 N_{SPT}$ for stress increments of 100kPa in excess of in situ effective stress. Buggy et al. (2016) reviewed the work of Stroud & Butler and updated the data with the results of settlements measurement on several sites in Ireland which included fourteen monitored locations, mostly at strain levels between 0.25% and 3%. The average fines contents of these sites was typically from 29% to 46% and the average I_p ranged from 6 to 24% with the majority of the sites considered to represent lodgement, ablation and englacial till deposits. Buggy and et. al.(2016) concluded that E_v'/N_{SPT} was loosely correlated to I_p , however the scatter is very large – see Figure 14, and many of the results fall below the suggested design line of Stroud & Butler. One of the many limitations of using the standard penetration test in glacial soils is the large scatter and the effect of stones on the results, as is shown by the results from the Tallaght footing test site on Figure 15. Taking N_{SPT} of 55 as representing the soil matrix on that site, together with the (conservative) interpreted E_v' of 80MPa, the E_v'/N_{SPT} for the Tallaght footing test is highlighted on Figure 14. Given the known complex relationships between soil stiffness and its stress history etc., together with the severe limitations of the SPT, such relationship as presented on Figure 14 are necessarily very approximate.

Buggy et al.(2016) also interpreted a coefficient of consolidation (c_v) from these case histories and concluded that the results were consistent with the NAVFAC (1982) relationship between c_v and liquid limit – see Figure 16.

Figure 14 E_v/N_{SPT} vs I_p from Buggy et al. (2016)

Figure 15 N_{SPT} vs depth Tallaght

Figure 16 Estimated c_v vs w_L from Buggy et al. (2016)

Geophysical methods have been used successfully to obtain the small strain shear modulus (G_0) of boulder clays using the relationship $G_0 = \rho V_s^2$ where ρ = density and V_s is the shear wave velocity. The Multi Channel Analysis of Surface Waves (MASW) method is currently the most commonly used method, however there are some recent developments

in the use of other methods, such as the Continuous Surface Wave (CSW) which may be adaptable for more general use. The G_0 obtained from these methods can be used to get an stiffness modulus at the appropriate strain from, for example, an appropriate normalised shear modulus and shear strain relationship as presented by Vardanega & Bolton (2013). This approach gives the possibility of overcoming some of the difficulties of obtaining reliable in-situ parameters of low fines diamictons, however further research is needed to compare actual performance with predications to give confidence for routine design. Long (2015) carried out a very comprehensive review of the current state of the art in this area, including tests in glacial deposits, which showed good correlations between V_s and the stiffness properties of the soils which reflect the in-situ stress conditions, such as the preconsolidation pressure (σ'_c) and undrained shear strength (c_u) but poor correlations with the coefficient of consolidation (c_v), the Janbu m coefficient (which represents the behaviour of the soil beyond the preconsolidation/yield pressure) and the Janbu creep parameter (r_s). The good correlation between undrained shear strength (c_u) and V_s for Irish glacial soils recorded by Long et al. (2013) is shown on Figure 17.

Figure 17 c_u versus v_s for Irish glacial soils (Long et al., 2013)

UNDRAINED STRENGTH

The relevance of the undrained shear strength of a boulder clay depends on the particular design situation as it is related to the length of time that pore water pressures/suctions set up by loading/unloading can be maintained. Several particular behaviour patterns of boulder clay and low fines diamictons have been evident in recent projects, namely:-

- High undrained shear strength of the Dublin lodgement tills
- The limited period of 'undrained' conditions of low fines diamictons with low fines as evident from 'reduced stand-up' time in excavations.
- The ability to construct embankments without a shear failure on low fines diamictons with low N_{SPT} values.

Research and field experience has shown that the undrained shear strength of the Dublin lodgement till is very high. This high undrained strength is shown on the isotropically consolidated triaxial compression tests (CIUC) on GeoboreS samples from boulder clay deposits recovered during the investigations for the Dublin Central Project in O'Connell Street in the centre of the city with c_u values of between 200 and 800kPa being recorded –see Figure 18. Surprisingly given the expected sample disturbance, on that project, the simple undrained triaxial tests (UU tests) on U100 samples recorded similar results, which is in agreement with the experience of Long & Menkiti (2007) for UU tests on high quality samples. There is, however, difficulty in practice in getting U100 samples of boulder clays due to the high stone content. The high undrained shear strengths measured in the laboratory are consistent with those inferred in the field from pull-out tests reported in Menkiti et al (2014) and shown on Figure 19 where skin resistance in the clayey DBC were typically in the 300 to 600kPa range, increasing with depth. Similar high shaft resistances were reported in instrumented pile compression tests which are discussed in later sections of this paper.

As stated previously, for routine design, the undrained shear strength is frequently inferred from the crude N_{SPT} , hence it is useful to compare the results of sophisticated testing with such relationships for the Dublin boulder clay. Farrell & Lawler (2007) considered that the relationship $c_u \approx 6 \times N_{SPT}$ kPa is a reasonable approximation ($I_p=11$) based on in-situ tests carried out on the St James Hospital site- see Figure 20, however the scatter in values is large.

A review of the results of two motorway projects by the author showed a very large scatter in the relationship of c_u from UU tests and N_{SPT} values recorded in the strata – see Figure 21, however the mean was about $c_u \approx 5.5 \times N_{SPT}$. A CIUC test at a confining stress approximately equivalent to its in-situ value (assuming $K_0=1$) gave an undrained shear strength consistent with this relationship (A on Figure 21), however, not surprisingly, CIUC tests under confining stresses higher than its in-situ stress gave higher strength values (Samples B on Figure 21). This highlights the need to estimate the in-situ stress conditions which requires an estimate of the lateral stress. Lawler et al. (2011) have estimated K_0 for the DBC but there is no information on that appropriate for other boulder clays.

The DBC generally has a significant fines content which results in a low permeability and generally good 'stand up', as was evident in the 12m deep trial excavation carried out for the cut & cover section of the Dublin Port Tunnel. However glacial deposits are not uniform and pockets or zones of lower fines or of sand layers can occur as is evident in the collapse of the trial section mentioned above after about 1.5 months due to the presence of sand layers (Kovacevic et al. 2008). While a marginal fines content reduces the stand-up time of vertical faces, the increased permeability generally means that relatively high embankments can be constructed on such low fines boulder clay even if strength indicators, such as N_{SPT} s or UU test or tactile inspection of the soil in trial pits, indicate that the initial undrained strength is relatively low (Coppinger and Farrell, 2003).

Figure 18 Undrained shear strength in DBC

Figure 19 Measured bond strength in pull-out anchor tests (Menkiti et al. 2014).

Figure 20 c_{uUU} vs $6 \times N_{SPT}$ kPa (Lawler and Farrell, 2007)

Figure 21 c_{uUU} & c_{uCIUC} vs $5.5xN_{SPT}$ kPa

PERMEABILITY

The permeability of boulder clay is a significant factor in the design of flood levees, in developing low permeability liners for landfill and other applications, and also in the aquifer vulnerability assessment studies carried out on behalf of the Geological Survey of Ireland (Misstear & Brown, 2008; Hunter Williams et al, 2013).

Some interesting studies have been carried out in recent years that compare the permeability measured in the field with that measured in the laboratory, and also into the sensitivity of permeability to the percentage of fines in a boulder clay/diamicton.

While it is appreciated that the coefficient of permeability (k) is a function of many factors, including the void ratio, viscosity of fluid, stress history and hydraulic gradient, in most geotechnical design situations the fluid is water and the in-situ stresses are relatively low and are not considered to have a significant effect. Consequently laboratory tests are typically carried out in triaxial cells on material compacted using 2.5kg rammer energy level, or on undisturbed samples, all of which are saturated when tested. Farrell et al. (2003) investigated the relationship between % fines (<0.063mm) and k which showed that low values of less than 10^{-8} m/s were measured on compacted and undisturbed samples of glacial till with greater than 30% fines, apart from some exceptions, for example Sample A on Figure 22. Inspection revealed that these exceptions had been compacted dry of optimum which resulted in a significantly higher k than measured on samples compacted wet of optimum with the same void ratio – see Figure 23. The variation of k with the moisture condition value (MCV), which is empirically related to the moisture content of a soil and is typically used to set site control limits for fill acceptability, illustrates the significance of the compaction moisture content on the resulting permeability for a fixed compactive effort- see Figure 24.

Swartz et al. (2003) also compared the laboratory determined k values with those from in-situ variable head

tests in standpipes – see Figure 25. Data from a project in Cork (Monard – from AGL files) is also shown on that figure. The in-situ values would inevitably include local permeable layers in the glacial till as well as any fissures that may be present, and consequently would be expected to be higher than the laboratory values on isolated samples, nevertheless the trend in the results would give confidence that the laboratory values are consistent with the field behaviour. The results confirm the expected increase in k value with reduction in the fines content. It should be stated that Swartz et al. (2003) considered that a better correlation was obtained between k and % clay content (particles <0.002mm) than with the fines content (<0.063mm), however there is considerably more data on the fines content as particle size distribution analyses are frequently limited to this size particle in geotechnical investigations.

Figure 22 k versus % fines – lab. tests

Figure 23 e versus moisture content

Figure 24 k versus MCV

Figure 25 k versus % fines, lab. & field test

PILE CAPACITY

The routine practice in the country is to select the length and diameter of a pile to carry design loads based on ground properties and to verify the design by pile tests. In practice, the estimation of pile capacity in boulder clays is still an undrained design assuming a shaft resistance of αc_u , and ultimate toe resistance of $N_c c_u$, (where α = adhesion factor and N_c = bearing resistance factor), with c_u generally being derived from empirical correlations with the crude standard penetration test. This section looks at the reliability of these correlations based on practical experience.

Unsurprisingly, the capacity of piles in the Dublin lodgement till has received most attention, including some interesting results on instrumented driven and CFA piles as shown on Figures 26 and 27. Instrumented pile tests, as would be expected, have shown that the toe resistance of a driven pile in DBC is significantly greater than that of a CFA, with N_c of about 55 indicated for the driven pile and about 9 for the CFA. The distribution of shaft shear stress for both types of piles does not conform with an approximately constant value which would be expected if it were related to αc_u and a constant c_u , however it is acknowledged that neither test mobilised the failure resistance. It is interesting to note that the shear stresses mobilised on the shaft are in the region of 300 to 400kPa which reflect the high undrained shear strength of DBC.

Galbraith et al. (2014) compiled a database of 175 static load tests on mainly driven and CFA piles in Ireland. Not all of the load tests had been taken to failure, however Galbraith used those which had been taken to failure (taken as 10% of the pile diameter) to show that a Chin extrapolation taking $\delta / \delta_f > 50\%$ (δ = maximum measured settlement, $\delta_f = 0.1D$ where D is the effective pile diameter) gave an estimated failure load ($R_{c,est}$) within 85 to 100% of the actual measured value ($R_{c,m}$) – see Figure 28. For DBC, it was concluded from the instrumented load tests that $c_u \approx 5.5 N_{SPT} kPa$; $\alpha = 0.8$ and that $N_c = 6.5$ and 65 for CFA and driven piles respectively. The calculated resistance from ground tests results ($R_{c,calc}$), mainly N_{SPT} values, and pile failure load estimated from the load tests ($R_{c,est}$) for CFA and driven piles in DBC are compared on Figures 29 and 30. The spread of the results is indicative of the uncertainties when designing piles from ground parameters and this is relevant to the selection of partial factors. It should be noted that some piles driven into DBC experienced false sets and that

redriving was necessary to get the required capacity (Armishaw & Bunni, 1992).

Not surprisingly, the high bearing resistance factor (N_c) measured in the DBC for driven piles is related to the in-situ density and has not been experienced in other less dense boulder clays which were driven to a depth, rather than a set, or where the set was less than required for the design capacity. Cast-in-situ piles were driven on a site in Waterford to determine if the required capacity was achieved at a specific depth rather than at a given set. Several of the piles failed to reach the required capacity and a standard calculation on these piles would suggest that $N_c \approx 9$. On that site a stiff brown sandy gravelly clay (glacial till) with moisture contents, gradings and N_{SPT} values shown on Figures 31 to 33, underlay 5.45 to 10.8m of peat. Rockhead varied but was about 18m below ground level. Notably, chiselling was required to penetrate cobbles/boulders in the glacial till, as is illustrated on Figure 33, however this local hard boring was not reflected in the pile capacity and this is not untypical of other sites. An example of one of the static load tests is that on Trial Pile 1 (480mm dia.) which indicated a failure load of 720kN for 3m penetration into the glacial till. This capacity is consistent with $f_1 = 5.5$, $N_{SPT} = 25$, $\alpha = 0.8$ and $N_c = 9$ and not with $N_c = 65$, as can be seen from Figure 34.

Figure 26 Distribution of shaft friction on driven pile in DBC (Farrell et al., 1998).

Figure 27 Distribution of shaft friction on CFA pile in DBC (after Farrell & Lawler, 2007).

Figure 28 $R_{c,calc}/R_{c,m}$ versus δ/D

Figure 30 Comparison of $R_{c,calc}$ & $R_{c,est}$ for driven piles in DBC ($N_c=65$)

Figure 29 Comparison of $R_{c,calc}$ versus $R_{c,est}$ for CFA piles in DBC ($N_c=6.5$)

Figure 31 Moisture contents in glacial till versus depth, Waterford.

Figure 32 PSDs recorded in the glacial till. Waterford.

Figure 33 N_{SPT} versus elevation in glacial till, Waterford.

Figure 34 $R_{c,calc}$ versus $R_{c,m}$ for $N_c = 65$, DCIS pile in Waterford.

SLOPES

The stability of slopes in boulder clays brings into focus the relationship between experience and geotechnical analyses. For example, the current practice is to construct road cut slopes in boulder clay soils and low fines diamictons at 1V:2H and such slopes have worked successfully provided local erosion is prevented by intercepting seepage layers using herringbone drains or a similar drainage system to prevent erosion of sandy particles where such seepage layers are encountered. Such slopes have stood the test of time (to date). Given that the residual angle of shearing resistance of the boulder clay is close to its constant volume value (Loughman, 1979), the remoulding of the soil due to seasonal ground movement would not be expected to give rise to long term stability issues. Jennings (2003) reported the assessment of about 320 km (200 miles) of slopes >3m in height in overburden for Iarnrod Eireann's earthworks network in the southwest of Ireland. The slopes were in a variety of glacial deposits, however a firm to very stiff well-graded gravelly sandy clay of low plasticity, sometimes with a large proportion of coarse particles up to boulder size, was the most prominent. Cut slopes were generally 3m in height or greater, up to 20m, but generally less than 5m, with angles of 20° to 45° and only a few slopes with steeper angles, see Figure 35. About 90% of all cut slopes were at 30° or greater, with 40° being the most frequent angle. About 5% of slopes showed signs of minor mostly small-scale shallow failures. Major slope instability involving near full-height failure was identified on only about 1% of the slopes and these had a history of failure; first time failures were rare. Most of the railway slopes were constructed in the 1850s, thus confirming the long term stability of relatively steep slopes in boulder clays.

The average slope angle for all slopes was 38° which is considerably greater than the findings of highway cuttings in till in the UK (Perry, 1989) where to limit failures then typically a slope of 5m should be between 16 and 27°.

Martinovic et al. (2016), carried out a statistical analysis of heights and slope angles determined from a LIDAR survey of the cuttings and embankments of the entire rail network in Ireland. The cuts and embankments of glacial soils were not highlighted, nevertheless the most frequent slope angle was between 36-38° for embankments and for cuts, similar to the findings of Jennings (2003).

Figure 35 from Jennings (2003)

Some major slope failures have occurred in 1V:2H slopes, however these can be explained by local geological features. A major slope failure in Donegal (see Figure 36), for example, was due to high water pressures in a local sand lamination in a stiff laminated clay and not in a boulder clay. Hughes et al.(2007) investigated the 1V:2H slope, 19m high, Dromore landslide which failed during a period of heavy rain after 30 years. The failure was attributed to strain softening, however a 0.6m thick layer of stiff clay which was found to be slickensided was possibly a major factor. Hughes et al. (2016) also documented the failure of a 25m deep road cutting in drumlin deposits in County Down which were caused by unrelieved hydrostatic pressures at the glacial till/rock interface.

Figure 36 Slope failure on Donegal Bypass

Despite the general experience on the stability of 1V:2H slopes in boulder clays/diamictons, it is necessary to assume relatively high shear strength parameters and a less than extreme phreatic surface in order to get a calculation to comply with the safety margins required by Eurocode 7 (current Eurocode 7 impose partial factors of 1.25 on c' and on $\tan \phi'$). For example, the typical shear strength parameters of a boulder clay (other than the DBC which has

higher values), based on 60mm square shear box tests or on 38mm triaxial samples would be $c' = 0$ and $\phi' = 34^\circ$. The use of such parameters does not give the required margin of safety when a phreatic surface of, for example, 1m below ground surface is assumed – see Figure 37. Various factors could account for the practical evidence that the margin of safety of boulder clay slopes at 1V:2H is greater than indicated in calculations, for example the effect of stone content and low effective stress could justify a higher ϕ' , however the computed value is very dependent on the hydrogeological profile assumed. The hydrogeological profile would be further complicated by differences between the permeability of the upper and lower till deposits as observed by Hughes et al. (2016). The only measurement of pore water pressures in cut slopes in typical boulder clay which was available to the author was from a 16.5m deep cut on the N7 south of Monasterevin, Co. Kildare which is shown on Figure 38. These measurements did show the expected drawdown with time but appear to be inconsistent. The seasonal variations in water pressures, as reported by Smethurst (2006) and the influence of vegetation (Scott et al., 2007) also have to be included in future slope design methods.

Figure 37 Typical analysis of stability of 1V:2H slopes.

Figure 38 Pore pressure measurements in N7 slope at Monasterevin, Co. Kildare.

Irish Sea Till

Departing from the theme of unsorted tills but remaining on the topic of slope stability, the fine grained Irish Sea till which is found on the south east and south coast of the country offers some particular challenges. This till, which is commonly referred to colloquially as Macamore Clay, has been identified as a band extending inland to a maximum of about 8km along the east coast of Ireland and up to about 1 to 3km inland on the south coast (O’Cofaigh et al, 2012). Comparison of the Teagasc soil map and the on-line quaternary geological map of the Geological Survey of Ireland shows the area assigned to Macamore Clay to be similar to that assigned to Irish Sea till, although the Irish Sea till is separated into Irish Sea till from limestone and Irish Sea till from lower Palaeozoic sandstones and shales. This glacial till, which is sometimes referred to as a boulder clay, is significant in geotechnical terms in that it has few if any gravel particles and typically has a fines content in excess of 70% and frequently greater than 90%, with some typical particles size distribution curves shown on Figure 39. This deposit does contain shell fragments, however significantly, no in-situ paired bivalves have been observed and O’Cofaigh et al. (2012) conclude from this and from other observations that it was deposited by a grounded Irish Sea Ice Stream. The Irish Sea till is overconsolidated, as can be inferred from the moisture contents compared with the Atterberg limits on Figure 40, and is generally a stiff intermediate to high plasticity Clay (see Figure 41), sometimes with sand layers or laminations.

The availability of Geological Survey of Ireland’s digitised data facilitates the study of the relationship between geological and geotechnical information by enabling data to be plotted using GIS methods. An example of this is shown on Figure 42 by the close correlation of the % fines recorded in ags data for the N11 from Gorey to Enniscorthy on the Quaternary Map of the Geological Survey of Ireland with the area designated as Irish Sea till.

Given the high fines content of the Irish Sea till, it is not surprising that the effective angle of shearing resistance is significantly less than that of the unsorted tills. The results of consolidated undrained triaxial and of direct shear box tests are shown on Figure 43 and Figure 44 respectively, and these indicate that a $c'=0kPa$ and a $\phi'=27$ or 28° is probably appropriate. The residual strength angle of shearing resistance is about 24° , however this may depend on particular layers within the till. These values are significantly less than the values recorded in stony till. Given these lower values of ϕ' than in stony tills found elsewhere in Ireland, flatter slope angles would be expected. Iarnrod Eireann kindly supplied data on a Lidar slope survey for the stretch of railway between 85km and 90km on Figure 45, which goes through the

Macamore Clay. The boreholes for which data on the Macamore Clay is available are shown as stars on Figure 46. Interrogating these slope data surprisingly shows similar distribution of stable slope angles as reported by Jennings (2003) for glacial till slopes elsewhere, as the cut slopes are generally between 35 and 45° – see Figure 47, with poor relationship between slope angle and slope height – see Figure 48, which could be due to the stabilising effects of vegetation and lower phreatic surface than generally taken in design. Notwithstanding this, it is usual practice to adopt 1V:2.5H or 1V:3H slopes in road cuttings in Macamore clay.

Figure 39 Typical grading curve of Irish Sea Till

Figure 40 Index test versus depth – Irish Sea till.

Figure 41 Irish Sea till on Plasticity Chart

Figure 42 % fines recorded on M11

Figure 43 CUD triaxial on Irish Sea till

Figure 44 Direct shear box tests on Irish Sea till.

Figure 45 Slope between 85km and 95km in Irish Sea

Figure 46 Location of Irish Sea till on SE coast (stars represent borehole locations).

Figure 47 Frequency of cut slopes

Figure 48 Depth of cutting vs slope angle.

EARTHWORKS

No major systemic construction issues relating to the behaviour of unsorted cohesive till (>15% fines) have been experienced in the earthworks of the extensive motorway programme which has been constructed over the last 30 years, other than perhaps the failure of the laboratory testing to reliably predict the acceptability of excavated material for use in embankments. The embankments have generally performed satisfactorily.

The criteria generally adopted for acceptable material for general embankment fill, for example, is to require a $CBR \geq 2\%$ and $\rho_d \geq 0.95 \times \rho_{dmax2.5kg}$ where $\rho_{dmax2.5kg}$ is the maximum dry density obtained when compacted using the 2.5kg rammer energy level. The compacted properties of unsorted till are notoriously sensitive to variations in moisture content and generally the design criteria are related to MCV for site control. Thus, for example, the CBR after

compaction is typically related to the MCV as shown in Figure 49. Davitt (1984) proposed the following two relationships based on his experience, however the spread between the values is large and it is difficult to justify the use of two relationships.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Log CBR} &= -0.75 + 0.137\text{MCV} & \text{Eq. 1 (Fine Till)} \\ \text{Log CBR} &= -0.65 + 0.14\text{MCV} & \text{Eq. 2 (Coarse Till)} \end{aligned}$$

The reliable prediction of the amount of cut material that can be used in embankments is an important factor in the preparation of cost effective tender submissions for motorways. However, the general experience is that the quantities of acceptable material are significantly underestimated if only the CBR and MCV values at natural moisture content are used in these evaluations. Rutty & Johnston (2012) reviewed three case histories which showed, for example, that whereas MCV in ground investigation would indicate that only about 40% was acceptable, the N_{SPT} values indicated about 75% acceptable which is closer to the actual value of about 90% recorded in construction. Both O'Donnell (2012) and Rutty & Johnson (2012) highlight the need to consider both N_{SPT} and soil descriptions when assessing the acceptability of boulder clays for embankment fill. The empirical correlations generally used are $c_u \approx 5.5 N_{SPT}$ kPa and c_u (kPa) ≈ 25 CBR%. Both authors emphasise the importance of the experience of the Contractor in handling low plasticity tills.

The difficulties with dealing with low fines diamictons (unsorted tills) in earthworks are discussed in O'Donnell (2012) where those with non-plastic or low plasticity fines are described as behaving like 'low slump concrete' when excavated below the water table. Such tills are very susceptible to changes in condition with very small changes in moisture content. Their condition can be improve significantly with drying, however winter working is extremely difficult and lime is sometimes successful in improving its workability.

Figure 49 CBR versus MCV

CONCLUSION

This paper presents a view of the current geotechnical engineering practice in glacial soils in Ireland, as an update to that given in Hanrahan (1977).

The glacial soils, which cover much of the country, were laid down in complex depositional and environmental conditions of the last (Midlandian) glaciation with only a few isolated locations of interglacial soils. The only significant deposit of interglacial soil identified to date in on the Cork Harbour area.

The more familiar term 'boulder clay', is used for lodgement and englacial tills in this paper although it is accepted a 'glacial diamicton' would possibly be a more appropriate description of these unsorted or poorly sorted deposits with a wide range of particle sizes and not just clay and boulders. The inclusion of the term 'clay' in geotechnical descriptions implies certain behaviour characteristics, such as a certain 'stand-up time' for shallow vertical cuts, however the fines content of some of these soils is relatively low which makes their behaviour marginal between a cohesive and granular material. The low fines unsorted tills are referred to as low fines diamictons in this paper.

There have been significant developments in sampling boulder clays and in determining their stiffness, strength and consolidation characteristics. Soil models have been developed for incorporation in numerical analyses and such models have been validated in field tests and in case studies. There are, however, difficulties in sampling low fines diamictons due to their limited ability to hold suction pressures and due to their stone content, and these issues also affect the results of in-situ tests. Pragmatism has led to the overuse of the crude N_{SPT} in geotechnical design and further developments are required to give a more rational approach to determining their in-situ geotechnical behaviour. Geophysics may offer a useful tool in this regard.

High undrained shear strengths have been recorded in laboratory tests on the very stiff Dublin black boulder clay and these laboratory strengths are consistent with field experience. While the 'undrained strength' of low fines diamictons is questionable, the practical experience is that in many cases such soil are able to support embankments of significant height.

The permeability of boulder clays and low fines diamictons is relevant to many geotechnical design situations and recent research has shown that this parameter can be related to the percentage fines provided cognisance is taken of the method of compaction. Field tests also show that the laboratory results are consistent with field permeability.

Instrumented pile tests have shown the high toe resistance achieved in driven piles in the very stiff DBC, where N_c values of the order of 65 have been interpreted. Not surprisingly, these high end resistances have not been achieved in less dense boulder clays, however trial load tests indicate that an N_c of 9 may be appropriate for stiff boulder clays with an N_{SPT} of about 25.

With regard to the stability of slopes in boulder clays, 1V:2H slopes have performed satisfactorily provided slope drainage measures are taken, where necessary, to prevent internal erosion. Failures that have been recorded in such

slopes are relatively rare and have been due to local specific geological conditions. There is an issue in justifying such slopes analytically as it requires an assessment of the hydrogeological conditions, in particular the phreatic line under appropriate environmental conditions, and research is being undertaken to get more information on this.

The Irish Sea till deposits, commonly referred to as Macamore Clay, are encountered on the south east of the country. Such glacial deposits have a grading more typical of a lacustrine or marine deposit with about 60% to 90% fines. This till is generally stiff in-situ, thus is overconsolidated, and has effective stress angles of shearing resistance significantly less than the more stony and lower plasticity boulder clays. Slope angles of 1V:2.5H or flatter are currently adopted in these deposits, although an analysis of the stability of the historic railway slopes show similar steep angles to those recorded in unsorted glacial deposits elsewhere.

The significant motorway construction programme of the last few years has shown the satisfactory performance of boulder clays compacted in accordance with the NRA Specification. Notwithstanding this satisfactory performance of the placed materials, there has been a notable failure of the laboratory testing methods currently used to reliably predict the acceptability of excavated material for use in embankments.

REFERENCES

- Armishaw J.W. and Bunni N. G., 1992, Driven precast concrete piles in Dublin black boulder clay. In *Piling in Europe*, Thomas Telford, London, 219-226.
- Benz, T, 2006, Small-strain stiffness of soils and its numerical consequences. PhD thesis, Institut fur Geotechnick, Universitat Stuttgart, (cited by Plaxis 2006)
- Boulton G.S , Paul M.A., 1976, The influence of genetic processes on some geotechnical properties of glacial tills *Q.J. Engng Geol.* 9, 159-194
- Buggy F, Kissane P, Rush D and Long M, *The performance of Road Embankments on Glacial Deposits in Ireland*, 2016, Civil Engineering Research in Ireland 2016 (CERI 2016), 697-702.
- Coppinger J and Farrell E.R, 2003, *Kildare Town Bypass-Design and Construction*, Institution of Engineers of Ireland.
- Coxon P, 2001 *Cenozoic:Tertiary and Quaternary (until 10,000 years before present)*, The Geology of Ireland Ed. By Charles Hepworth Holland, Dunedin Academic Press.p387-427
- Coxon P, and Dowling L, 2015, *Interglacial deposits in Cork Harbour*, Quaternary Research Association, Irish Quaternary Association Field Guide, pp147-157,
- Davitt S, 1984, The use of the moisture condition test in assessing soils for roadworks, Report RC278, Environmental Research Unit, Nov.

- Farrell E. R., 2010, Lessons learnt – problems to solve, BCRI Conf. Uni. College Cork.
- Farrell, E.R, Bunni, N.G., Mulligan J., 1987, The bearing capacity of Dublin black boulder clay, IEL, Vol 112, pp77-104.
- Farrell E. R. Coxon P, Doff D, Pried’homme L 1995a, Genesis of brown boulder clay in Dublin, *Quarterly Journal of Engineering Geology*, 28, 143-152.
- Farrell E.R and Lawler M., 2007, ‘CFA pile behaviour in very stiff lodgement till’, *Geotechnical Engineering*, 161, 49-57, 2007
- Farrell E.R., Lehane B.M., and Looby M., 1998, Instrumented driven pile in Dublin boulder clay, *Geotechnical Engineering*, 131, 4, 1998, 233-241
- Farrell E.R. Lehane B and O’Brien S, 1995b ‘Stiffness of Dublin black boulder clay’, *Proc. XI ECSMFE*, 1, 109-114.
- Farrell E.R., Misstear B.D.R., and Orr T.L.L., 2003, Permeability of well graded till, Proc. XIII European Conference on Soil Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering, Prague.
- Funnell, B.M. 1995 Global sea-level and the (pen)insularity of late Cenozoic Britain. In:Preece, R.C. (ed.) *Island Britain:a Quaternary Perspective*. Geological Society Special Publication No. 96,pp, 3-13
- Galbraith A., 2011, Design and Performance of Deep Foundations in Ireland, PhD thesis, University of Dublin, Trinity College, Dublin, Ireland.
- Galbraith A, Farrell E.R. and Byrne J., 2014, Assessment of uncertainty in pile resistance from static load tests using a database, *Geotechnical Engineering*, GE5, Oct, 431-446
- Hanrahan, E.T, 1977, Irish Glacial Till:Origin and Characteristics, An Foras Forbartha, RC 164.
- Hughes D.A.B, Clarke G.R.T, Harley D.M.G & Barbour S.L., 2016, The impact of hydrogeology on the instability of a road cutting through a drumlin in Northern Ireland, *Quarterly Jnl. Engn. Geol& Hydrogeology*, 49, 92-104.
- Hughes D.A.B., Sivakuman V., Glynn D. Clarke G, 2007, A case study:delayed failure of a deep cutting in lodgement till, *Geot. Engn.*, Oct. GE4, 193-202.
- Hunter Williams N. H., Misstear B.D.R., Daly D and Lee M., 2013, *Quarterly Jnl. Of Engng. Geology and Hydrogeology*, Vo. 46, 493-506.
- Hays, J.D, Imbrie, N.J, Shackleton N.J, 1976, Variations in the Earth’s Orbit, Pacemaker of the Ice Ages, *Science*, New Series, Vol. 194, No. 4270.
- Lehane B.M and Simpson B, 2000, Modelling glacial till under triaxial conditions using a BRICK soil model, *Can. Geotech. Jnl.* 37:1078-1088.
- Jennings P, 2003, Performance of 150 year-old railway slopes in glacial till:case study from southwest Ireland, Proc. XIII ECSMGE, Prague.
- Jouzel, J, Lorius C, Petit, J.R., Genthon C., Barkov, N.I, Kotlyankov, V.M, and Petrov, V.M., 1987, *Nature* 329:403-8
- Jouzel, J, Barkov, N.I., Barnola, J.M., Bender M, Chappellaz, J., Genthon C, Kotlyskov, V.M, Lipenkov, V. Lorius C., Petit, J.R, Raunaud, D., Raisback, G., Ritz C., Sowers T, Stievenard, M, Yiou, F. and Yiou P, 1993, Extending the vostok ice-core record of palaeoclimate to penultimate glacial period, *Nature* 364:407-12.
- Jouzel, J, Waelbroeck, C, Malaize, B, Bender M, Petit, J.R, Stievenard M, Barkov, N.I, Marnola, J.M, King t, Kotlyakov, V.M. Lipenkov V, Lorius C, Raynaud, D, Ritz C, Sowers T, 1996 Climatic interpretations of the recently extended Vostok ice records, *Climate Dynamics* 12:513-521
- Kovacevic N, Milligan G.W.E, Menkiti, C.O., Long M, Potts D.M., 2008, Finite element analysis of steep man-made cuts in Dublin boulder clay, *Can. Geotech. J.* 45:549-559.
- Kovacevic N, Menkiti, C.O., Long M, Potts D.M., 2015, Finite element analysis of a cantilever wall in Dublin boulder clay, Proc. XVI ECSMGE, ICE Publishing, pp3983-3988
- Lawler, M, Farrell E.R and Lochaden A.L.E, (2011) Comparison of the measured and finite element-predicted ground deformations of a stiff lodgement till, *Can. Geotech. J.* 48:98-116
- Lisiecki L.E, and Raymo M.E, A Pliocene-Pleistocene stack of 57 globally distributed benthic $\delta^{18}O$ records, *Paleoceanography* 20, 1003.
- Long M, 2015, Developments in the use of geophysics in geotechnical engineering in soft ground, Proc. XVI ECSMGE, Geotechnical Engineering for Infrastructure and Development, ICE.
- Long, M., 2015, Developments in the use of geophysics in geotechnical engineering in soft ground, Proc. XVI ECSMGE, Edinburgh, 129-150.
- Long M and Menkiti C., 2007, Geotechnical properties of Dublin boulder clay, *Geotechnique*, 57 (7), 595-611.
- Long M, Quigley P, and O’Connor P, 2013, Undrained shear strength and stiffness of Irish glacial till from shear wave velocity. *Ground Engineering*, 46(11) 26-27.
- Loughman, G. (1979). The residual shear strength of Irish glacial till. Unpublished MSc Thesis, University of Dublin, Trinity College.
- McCabe, A.M. and Hoare, P.G., 1978, The late Quaternary history of east central Ireland *Geological Magazine*, 115, 397-413.
- Martinovic K, Gavin K, Reale C, 2016a, Assessing the vulnerability of Irish rail network earthworks, *Transport Research Procedia*, 14, 1904-1913, Elsevier.

- Martinovic K, Gavin K, Reale C, 2016b, Landslide susceptibility assessment for engineered slopes using statistical and deterministic approaches, CERl, 479-484
- Menkiti C. O, Long M., Milligan G.W.E, and Higgins,O, 2014, Soil nailing in Dublin boulder clay, *Geotech Geol Eng* 32:1427-1438
- Missteart, B.D.R, & Brown, L. 2008. Recharge and groundwater vulnerability. ERTDI Programmer 2000-2006 Phase 3:Water Framework Directive. Environment Protection Agency, STRIVE Report Series, 6.
- Mitchell, G.F, 1973, Fossil pingos in Camaross Townland, Co. Wexford. *Proc. Royal Irish Academy, Sec. B, Vol.73* pp269-282.
- Mitchell, G. F. 1980 The search for Tertiary Ireland. *Jnl. of Earth Sciences Royal Dublin Society*, 3, 13-33
- Mitchell, G.F. 1985 The Preglacial landscape. In:Edwards, K.J. and Warren, W.P. (eds), *The Quaternary History of Ireland*. London:Academic Press, 17-37.
- O’Cofaigh C, & Evans, D.J.A, 2007, Radiocarbon constraints on the age of the maximum advance of the British-Irish Ice Sheet in the Celtic Sea, *Quaternary Science Reviews* 26, 1197-1203
- O’Cofaigh, C, Telfer M.W, Bailey R.M & Evans D.J.A, 2012, Late Pleistocene chronostratigraphy and ice sheet limits, southern Ireland, *Quaternary Science review* 44,pp 160-179.
- O’Cofaigh C and Evans, D.J.A, 2015 *Quaternary geology and glacial history, The Quaternary of South East Ireland, Field Guide* Ed. G McGlynn and B Stefanine, Quaternary Research Association, Irish Quaternary Association.
- O’Donnell C., 2012, *Proceedings of Conf. on Geotechnics on Irish Roads, 2000-2010: A decade of achievement*, Geotechnical Society of Ireland.
- Perry J, 1989, A survey of slope conditions on motorway earthworks in England and Wales, *Transport Research Laboratory, Crowthorne, Research RR199*.
- Petit, J.R, Louzel, J, Raynaud D, Barkov, N.I, Barnola J.M., Basile I, Bender M, Chappellaz J, Davis M, Delayque G, Delmotte M, Kotlyakov V.M, Legrand M, Lipenkov, V.Y, Lorius C, Pepin L, Ritz C, Saltzan E, Stievenard M, 1999, Climate and atmospheric history of the past 420,000 years from the Vostok ice core, Antarctica, *Nature* 399:426-436.
- Praeg D, McCarron S, Dove D, O Cofaigh C, Scott G Monteys X, Facchin L, Romeo R, Coxon P. 2015 Ice sheet extension to the Celtic Sea Shelf edge at the Last Glacial Maximum *Quaternary Science Reviews* 111, 107-112 .
- Rutty P.C & Johnston T.P , 2012, Optimum use of material; selection of limits for suitable earthworks fill:Irish Experience, *Geological Society of London, Engineering Geology Special Publication v26* p79-92.
- Schanz, T, Vermeer, P.A., and Bonnier, P.G, 1999, The hardening soil model: formulation and verification. *In* Beyond 2000 in computation geotechnics-10 years of Plaxis. Balkema pp 281-290.
- Scott, Loverage and O’Brien, 2007, Influence of climate and vegetation on railway embankments,
- Scourse J.D Austin W.E.N, Bateman R.M Catt J.A Evans C.D.R Robinson J.E Young J.R, 1990, Sedimentology and micropalaeontology of glacial marine sediments from the central and southwestern Celtic Sea. In Dowdeswell J A, Scourse J D (Eds) *Glacial marine environments: Processes and Sediments*. Geological Society (London) Special Publication 53 329-347.
- Scourse J.D, Allen, J.R.M, Austin, W.E.N, Devoy R.J.N, Coxon P, Sejrup H.P, 1992, New Evidence on the Age and Significance of the Gortian Temperature Stage:A preliminary report on the Cork Harbour Site, *Proc. R.I.Academy, Vol. 92B*, pp21-43
- Shackleton and Opdyke, 1976, Oxygen isotope and palaeomagnetic stratigraphy of Equatorial Pacific core V28-239, Late Pliocene to Latest Pleistocene. *Geological Soc. Of America Memoir*, 145, 449-464.
- Shackleton, N. J., Berger, A. and Peltier, W.R. 1991. An alternative astronomical calibration of the Lower Pleistocene times based on ODP Site 677. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Edinburgh*, 81, 252-261.
- Skipper J, Follett B, Menkiti C. O., Long M, Clark-Hughes J, 2005 *Quarterly Journal of Engineering Geology*, 38, 171-187.
- Smethurst J.A, Clarke D. & Powrie W, 2006, Seasonal changes in pore water pressure in a grass covered slope in London clay, *Geotechnique* 56, No. 8, 523-527.
- Stroud, M.A. and Butler F.G.,1975, The standard penetration test and the engineering properties of glacial material. *Proc. Sym. On The Engineering Behaviour of Glacial Materials*, University of Birmingham, April, Published by The Midlands Geotechnical Society, 117– 128.
- Swartz, M., Missteart, B.D.R., Daly D. & Farrell E.R. 2003. Assessing subsoil permeability for groundwater vulnerability. *Quarterly Journal of Engineering Geology and Hydrogeology*, 36, 73-184.
- Vardanega, P, J, and Bolton M,D, 2013, Stiffness of Clays and Silts:Normalised Shear Modulus and Shear Strain. *J. Geotech. Geoenviron. Eng.* 139:1575-1589.
- Warren W.P, 1991, Fenitian (Midlandian) glacial deposits and glaciation in Ireland and adjoining off-shore regions In *Glacial deposits in Great Britain and Ireland* (Eds, Ehlers J, Gibbard P.L, Rose J, A.A. Balkema, Rotterdam, 79-88

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to acknowledge the support from my colleagues in AGL Consulting in preparing this paper and also to thank Fintan Buggy, Chairman of the Geotechnical Society of Ireland, and the Committee of that Society for the honour of presenting this First Hanrahan Lecture.